

Synthesis of Substituted Stilbenes and Coumarins

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p-Iodophenylacetic acid has been condensed with benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-dimethylamino benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 5-bromo salicylaldehyde, 3:5-dibromo-salicylaldehyde and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde. Maximum yields obtained were 53.8%, 75.9%, 31.6%, 21.4%, 94.6%, 74.0%, 49.5%, 75.0%, 99.9% and 26.0% respectively.

Substituted stilbenes and coumarins have been prepared by the condensation of *p*-iodophenylacetic acid with substituted benzaldehyde. This series of experiments is a continuation of a study of the influence of substituents on the acid and aldehyde components in Knoevenagel reaction. Earlier results have already been published.^{1, 2, 3}

EXPERIMENTAL:

Preparation of p iodophenylacetic acid:—

p-Iodophenylacetic acid was prepared by the following series of reactions

Preparation of 5-bromo-salicylaldehyde and 3:5-dibromo-salicylaldehyde.

These were prepared as reported earlier.²

Condensation of p-Iodophenylacetic acid with Aryl aldehydes. With Benzaldehyde:— 0.20 gm. of *p*-iodophenylacetic acid (0.0007 mole), 0.08 gm. (0.0007 mole) of benzaldehyde and traces of different bases, viz., pyridine, piperidine, α -picoline, pyridine and acetic anhydride and triethylamine and acetic anhydride, were heated at different temperatures viz., 100, 120, 140, 145 and 160° for different durations of time viz., 6, 12 and 18 hr. The condensed product was extracted with ether and treated with 10% sodium-bicarbonate solution. The aqueous layer was removed and acidified with conc. HCl. The acid, so obtained, was recrystallised from alcohol and water and was found to be α -carboxy-4-iodo-stilbene, m. p. 175-6°. The above procedure was followed for the condensation of *p*-iodophenylacetic acid with several other aldehydes also. The results are given in the following table (I).

1. Vishnu Chandra and V.B. Srivastava, *This Journal*, 1966, 43, 433.
2. Vishnu Chandra and V.B. Srivastava, *This Journal*, 1966, 43, 796.
3. Vishnu Chandra and V.B. Srivastava, *This Journal*, 1967, 44, 675.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Aldehyde	Condensing agent	Time in hours	Product	M.P. in °C	Yield in %	Found	Analysis	Formula
1.	Benzaldehyde	(a) Piperidine (b) Py + Ac ₂ O	6	α-Carboxy-4-iodostilbene	175—6	53.8	I, 38%, NE 331.5	I, 38.2%, NE 332.2	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ IO ₂
2.	Anisaldehyde	(a) Piperidine (b) Py + Ac ₂ O	12	α-Carboxy-4-iodo-4-methoxy stilbene	175—6	12.4	I, 38%, NE 331.5	I, 38.2%, NE 332.3	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ IO ₂
3.	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	(a) Piperidine (b) *(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N + Ac ₂ O	12	—	191	75.9	I, 33.7%, NE 380.0	I, 33.4%, NE 380.1	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ IO ₃
4.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	(a) Piperidine (b) *(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N + Ac ₂ O	6	4-Iodo-4'-nitro-stilbene	204	29.4	I, 34.9%	I, 35.5%	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ INO ₂
5.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino benzaldehyde	(a) Py + Ac ₂ O (b) Piperidine	6	α-Carboxy-4-iodo-4'-nitro stilbene	250	31.6	I, 31.9%, NE 394.8	I, 32.1%, NE 395.13	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NOI
6.	Salicylaldehyde	(a) Py + Ac ₂ O (b) Piperidine	6	α-Carboxy-4-iodo-2'-nitro stilbene	155	21.4	I, 31.8%, NE 394.5	I, 32.1%, NE 395.13	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ INO ₄
7.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy benzaldehyde	(a) Py + Ac ₂ O (b) Piperidine	6	4-Iodo-4'-dimethylamino stilbene	240	94.6	I, 36.0%	I, 36.3%	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ NI
8.	5-Bromo salicylaldehyde	(a) Py + Ac ₂ O (b) Piperidine	12	3-(<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl)-Coumarin	192	25.5	I, 36.0%	I, 36.4%	C ₁₃ H ₉ IO ₂
9.	3:5-dibromo salicylaldehyde	(a) Py + Ac ₂ O (b) Piperidine	12	3-(<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl)-Coumarin	192	74.0	I, 36.0%	I, 36.4%	C ₁₃ H ₉ IO ₂
10.	<i>p</i> -Chloro benzaldehyde	(a) Py + Ac ₂ O (b) *(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N + Ac ₂ O	12	4-Iodo-4'-hydroxy stilbene	186	49.5	I, 39.3%	I, 39.4%	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ IO
		(a) Piperidine (b) Py + Ac ₂ O	12	3-(<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl)-6-bromo-coumarin	209	45.2	I, 29.6% Br, 18.65%	I, 29.7% Br, 18.7%	C ₁₃ H ₈ BrIO ₂
		(a) Piperidine (b) Py + Ac ₂ O	12	3-(<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl)-6-bromo-coumarin	210	75.0	I, 29.6% Br, 18.65%	I, 29.7% Br, 18.7%	C ₁₃ H ₈ BrIO ₂
		(a) Piperidine (b) Py + Ac ₂ O	18	3-(<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl)-6;8-dibromo-coumarin	249	64.2	I, 24.9% Br, 31.3%	I, 25.0% Br, 31.6%	C ₁₃ H ₇ Br ₂ IO ₂
		(a) Piperidine (b) *(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N + Ac ₂ O	6	3-(<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl)-6;8-dibromo-coumarin	249	99.9	I, 24.9% Br, 31.3%	I, 25.0% Br, 31.6%	C ₁₃ H ₇ Br ₂ IO ₂
		(a) Piperidine (b) *(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N + Ac ₂ O	6	α-Carboxy-4-iodo-4'-chloro-stilbene	214	26.0	Cl, 8.9% I, 32.4%	Cl, 9.08% I, 32.5%	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ClIO ₂

*Temperature in all cases except those marked with * was 140—145°. In examples marked * it was 100°

DISCUSSION

Some substituted stilbenes and coumarins were prepared earlier ^{1,2,3} by the condensation of *p*-chloro- and *p*-bromophenylacetic acids with substituted aryl aldehydes. *p*-Iodophenylacetic acid has now been condensed with a number of aldehydes (See table I).

The results (Table I) indicate that electron donor groups like -OCH₃, -N(CH₃)₂, -OH etc., when introduced in the aldehyde component, facilitate the reaction while electron acceptor groups like nitro group retard it, in presence of piperidine alone as the condensing agent. This observation is in line with the earlier findings in the condensations of *p*-chloro- and *p*-bromophenylacetic acids with substituted benzaldehydes.^{1,2,3} When the catalyst employed is a mixture of base and acetic anhydride, the above situation is reversed and electron acceptor groups facilitate the reaction and electron donor groups retard it. This latter observation is in agreement with the generally accepted view that electron acceptor groups on the aldehyde component facilitate the reaction and electron donor groups retard it, because the reaction involves a carbanion addition to the carbonyl groups.

As expected, *p*-iodophenylacetic acid has been found to be less reactive than *p*-chloro- and *p*-bromophenylacetic acids.^{1,2,3}

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